

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MANAGEMENT OF ECONOMIC SECURITY OF ENTERPRISES UNDER CONDITIONS OF MODERN CHALLENGES AND OBSTACLES

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the need to ensure the formation of an economic security management system, which should be considered as a set of interrelated elements that are separated from the environment and interact with it as a whole. The importance of prioritizing the choice among certain areas of enterprise development, the compliance of the strategy with intra-production processes, namely: the policy of managing the renewal of fixed assets, technical and technological re-equipment, the introduction of innovations, the system of motivation and development of personnel, environmental friendliness of production, is substantiated.

Keywords: management, enterprises, economy, development, strategy.

Introduction. Relevance of the research topic. In modern conditions of instability of the market environment, the development and functioning of business entities largely depend on a reliable and high-quality system for ensuring economic security. This is due to the high level of competition, the need for constant adaptation of the management system to dynamic changes in the market environment, and the need to prevent the negative impact of a complex of exogenous and endogenous threats.

Analysis of studies and publications. The theoretical foundations of the development of a system for ensuring the economic security of an enterprise are reflected in the works of domestic and foreign authors, such as Vaskova Yu. I. [3], Gudz O. E. [4], Galuschak V. V. [5], Demchenko I.V. [7], Lyashenko A. N. [10], Lavrova Yu. V. [11].

However, despite significant scientific works, some issues regarding the essence of the economic security of an enterprise and the definition of a system for its provision remain controversial and uncertain.

Purpose of the article. The purpose of the article is theoretical substantiation and the formation of practical aspects of managing the economic security of enterprises.

Presentation of the main material. In the conditions of market relations, when the state is no longer responsible for the results of the financial and economic activities of the enterprise, ensuring economic security becomes one of the most important and urgent problems of its functioning. The economic security of entrepreneurship is a universal category that reflects the security of subjects of socio-economic relations at all levels, from the state to each of its citizens. The content of this concept includes a system of means that ensures the competitiveness and economic stability of the enterprise, as well as contributes to an increase in the welfare of workers, and only by performing the necessary number of these actions will it be possible to achieve an appropriate level of economic security of the enterprise. The main task of the enterprise economic security management system is to predict and anticipate possible threats leading to a crisis state, as well as to conduct anti-crisis management, which is aimed at bringing the

enterprise out of the crisis state; minimizing external and internal threats to the economic state of a business entity, in particular, its financial, material, informational, human resources, based on the developed set of measures of an economic, legal and organizational nature [8]. The main functional goals of the economic security of the enterprise include:

- ensuring high financial efficiency of work, financial stability, and independence of the enterprise;
- ensuring technological independence and achieving high competitiveness of the technical potential of one or another business entity;
- achievement of high management efficiency, the optimal organizational structure of enterprise management;
- minimization of the destructive impact of the results of production and economic activities on the state of the environment;
- high-quality legal protection of all aspects of the enterprise's activities;
- ensuring the protection of the information field, and trade secrets and achieving the required level of information support for the work of all divisions of the enterprise and departments of the organization;
- effective organization of the safety of the personnel of the enterprise, it is capital and property, as well as commercial interests [9].

Ensuring economic security involves identifying, analyzing, and assessing the existing threats to each functional component and developing on their basis a system of countermeasures and precautions. The system of economic security of each enterprise is individual, its completeness and effectiveness depend on the legislative framework in force in the state, on the amount of material, technical and financial resources allocated by the heads of enterprises, on the understanding of each of the employees of the importance of ensuring business security, as well as on the experience of heads of security services enterprises. Also, the structural composition of the economic security system includes intra-production and non-production components. The following components of the economic security of an enterprise are distinguished: financial

component, intellectual component, personnel component, technological component, legal component, information component, environmental component, power component, and market component [5]. An enterprise, like a product, has its own life cycle and goes through several stages: creation, establishment in the market, maturity, and, possibly, decline. There are risks inherent in each stage. At the stage of formation, the risks of false pricing and sales policy, the formation of authorized capital, and others prevail, at the stage of maturity there are risks of a decrease in the size of equity capital, loss of image, non-fulfillment of buyers' accounts receivable, at the stage of a decline in business activity there is a risk of non-fulfillment of obligations under transactions, personnel, credit and the risk of insolvency [6]. The magnitude of the impact of risk depends not only on the size, age, and volume of financial resources of the enterprise but also on the type of products that the enterprise produces. It doesn't always have to be new products. Quite often, an enterprise thrives on improving the products it has already produced. Before producing products, you need to carefully study the market, namely: the product will be in demand, how much it can be sold in this market, at what price, and most importantly, the profit can be obtained as a result. Having studied the risks, it is possible to identify the main subjects that are potential carriers of threats to the economic activity of the enterprise. These include:

- a state with levers of influence - legislative framework, taxes, and loans;
- partner states in the implementation of export operations with a national legal framework and transport regulations, as well as their own tax and credit systems;
- competing enterprises capable of manufacturing

and selling products of similar quality;

- buyers whose consumer demand is constantly changing;
- production partners supplying raw materials and materials, the provision of various types of resources depends on the timely fulfillment of obligations.

As a result of the research, the following methods of risk mitigation were identified: reserve funds; risk insurance; searching and obtaining additional information on risk aversion; distribution of risk among participants; transfer of risk; diversification and limitation of risk t. If risks are not given due attention, they will inevitably become a real threat to the functioning and development of the enterprise.

The characteristic features of the modern economy of Ukraine are the presence of structural imbalances in national production, the shadow economy, its export orientation towards the predominant share of products with a low level of gross value added; critical dependence of the economy on imported energy sources; unfavorable investment and innovation climate; imperfection, inconsistency and lack of transparency in legislation; low solvency of individuals and legal entities, outdated technical and technological base of enterprises and their slow renewal, etc. The objective consequence of the current state of the Ukrainian economy is a decrease in the main macroeconomic indicators of the country.

Almost 660,000 businesses remained active in Ukraine in 2022. The total number of active enterprises in Ukraine as of November 1, 2022, was 659 755.

Most of them were engaged in such activities as (Fig 1):

Fig 1. Number of active enterprises in Ukraine as of the end of 2022

- activities of other public organizations not included in other groups – 93 046 enterprises;
- complex maintenance of objects – 61 370;
- cultivation of cereals (except rice), legumes and oilseeds – 36 982;
- leasing and operating own or leased real estate – 28 336;
- public administration of a general nature – 26 879;
- the activity of trade unions – 25 918;
- activities of religious organizations – 25 886;
- provision of other social assistance without provision of accommodation (not included in other groups) – 23 386;
- non-specialized wholesale trade – 19 925;
- general secondary education – 14 694.

At the present stage, most domestic enterprises, working in an unstable economic and socio-political environment, are experiencing a deep decline in production and are either in a critical state or in a state of

bankruptcy. The enterprise itself is the main structural and educational element of the state economy, therefore the economic security of the enterprise can play a special role in its further activities. Through the system of taxes, subsidies, loans, prices, and other instruments, the state implements its own policy, which can increase or decrease the overall assessment of the economic security of the enterprise in particular and, as a result, the state as a whole, since the state largely determines the external economic security of the enterprise. The level of economic security of an enterprise should be based on an analysis of its financial condition. The general financial condition of the enterprise is assessed on the basis of indicators reflecting the financial and economic activities of the enterprise, the availability, location, use, and movement of the enterprise's resources [14]. As you know, the main areas of analysis of the financial condition of the enterprise include analysis of indicators of the effectiveness of the financial and economic activities of the enterprise; analysis of the solvency and financial stability of the enterprise; analysis of the effectiveness of the use of financial resources of the enterprise; analysis of indicators for assessing the

effectiveness of the financial and economic activities of the enterprise.

Conclusions and offers. Thus, summing up, it should be noted that within the framework of the formation and implementation of mechanisms for managing the process of strengthening the economic security of enterprises as subjects of entrepreneurial activity, ensuring their economic security should be considered a type of management activity for the formation, development, and implementation of competitive advantages and ensuring the viability of enterprises as subjects. economic competition. Ensuring the economic security of an enterprise is a set of actions that include: analyzing potential economic threats, planning countermeasures, monitoring the implementation of measures taken, and analyzing the effectiveness of the economic security system. The formation of a system for managing the economic security of enterprises requires additional costs that do not bring quick income. In our opinion, it is possible to effectively implement the function of supporting the economic security of an enterprise by creating an internal economic security service. The composition and structure of the internal economic security service for various enterprises primarily depend on the magnitude of financial losses, the nature and scale of activities, market position, and financial capabilities of the enterprise. An effective factor in the formation of an effective system for managing the economic security of enterprises is the use of the services of external specialized state or private security organizations. Formation of the state of economic security of business entities requires a proper justification. In the context of the above, in scientific and practical terms, it is important to use an algorithm for the formation of the state of economic security of an enterprise, it is advisable to consider it as an element in its management decision-making system, substantiates the procedure for using a certain mechanism for ensuring economic security, which is implemented in response to the actual influence of risk factors through a separate functional component of economic security in a specific target area.

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